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Governing Mineral Extraction in the High North: *Lessons from the Nasa Mountain Mine*

POLICY BRIEF

Summary

The High North in Norway plays a strategic role in Europe's green transformation through its potential to supply critical minerals needed for renewable technologies, such as solar panels, batteries, and wind turbines. As Europe seeks to reduce dependency on imports from authoritarian regimes like China, and conflict-ridden countries like DR Congo, Norway's mineral resources, especially in rural and northern regions, are increasingly seen both as vital and more sustainable. However, the quartz extraction project at Nasa Mountain in Northern Norway reveals deep tensions between the global demands for so-called 'sustainable minerals' and local Indigenous rights, environmental concerns, and regional development. The case illustrates how fragmented governance, and conflicting priorities create a 'wicked problem' for local planners and raises several paradoxes. It also highlights the need for more integrated and holistic planning processes which balance the needs and objectives of all actors at all levels of governance (local, national, and international) simultaneously.

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Key Messages

- ⇒ Europe's Green Deal depends on mineral extraction but seeks to reduce critical minerals dependency on authoritarian regimes and human right abusers.
- ⇒ Northern Norway is rich in mineral resources, making it a strategic region for Europe's green transition causing various industry-companies to initiate local mineral extraction projects such as the NASA Mountain Quartz Case.
- ⇒ What may be beneficial globally, such as securing critical minerals for the green transition or avoiding financing human-rights abuses, can have negative local consequences, especially for Indigenous Sámi communities and the environment.
- ⇒ The proposed mining threatens reindeer herding areas, raising tensions between Sámi rights and state development goals.
- ⇒ Ownership behind local private extraction companies in a globalised world is often blurry. In the case of the Nasa Mountain Quartz Project, the company Salten Elkem is 98% owned by Blue Star, a Chinese company.
- ⇒ The planning process concerning mineral extraction involves actors at different governance levels, each with distinct priorities and legitimacy.
- ⇒ The planning process in the Nasa Mountain case (and others) is fragmented across various authorities and planning systems, which obscures the full complexity of the issue, as well as which actor that has overall general responsibility.
- ⇒ This fragmentation contributes to a 'wicked problem', a problem that is difficult to solve due to its complexities, including conflicting values and interests.
- ⇒ To grasp the complexity of local mineral extraction it is important that the key actors on all levels are identified along with their respective interests, as a first step within the planning to reveal the planning conflicts or paradoxes.

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Background

In 2014, Rana Municipality approved a zoning plan permitting open-pit quartz mining at Nasa Mountain in Northern Norway. The 5km² site is targeted by Elkem Salten ASA, a subsidiary of Elkem, whose majority shareholder is China National Bluestar. Elkem listed on the Norwegian stock exchange in 2018, with BlueStar retaining its majority stake. The high-purity quartz is intended for Elkem's silicon plant located about 100km north of the site. Initially welcomed by the municipality for its economic benefits, the project was later framed by Elkem as part of the global green transition, aligning with the EU's 2019 Green Deal (Mo Industripark 2014).

To meet climate goals, the EU aims to cut greenhouse gas emissions by 55% by 2030, which makes the green transition a top priority. However, this shift depends heavily on access to critical minerals like cobalt, lithium, and rare earths, which are essential for technologies such as wind turbines, electric vehicles, and batteries (European Environmental Agency, 2026).

Many critical raw minerals needed for the green transition are sourced from politically unstable regions, raising concerns about human rights, child labour, and environmental harm. For example, almost 70% of the world's cobalt comes from the Democratic Republic of Congo, where mining is often linked to violence and exploitation (Gulley, 2022). To address these issues, the EU is pushing for more sustainable and ethically sourced minerals, ideally from democratic countries. Another concern is Europe's reliance on China, which dominates global rare earth production. This dependency has become more pressing due to geopolitical tensions and the war in Ukraine (Stjernström et al 2024), and more recently, Iran.

As part of this agenda, Norway (and Northern Norway in particular) has become a focal point for exploration and extraction. The Norwegian Government's 2025 white paper on industrial policy, outlines a strategic commitment to developing what they refer to as "a sustainable and competitive mineral industry", with Northern Norway playing a central role. The region's strategic location and resource potential make it a cornerstone of Norway's national effort to support the green transition and reduce dependency on external actors, such as China (Regjeringen, 2023).

However, the push for mineral extraction raises complex questions about environmental risks and Indigenous rights, with impacts ranging from local pollution to global climate effects. It should also be noted, the social consequences of this development vary. While some actors might benefit economically, others face loss of livelihoods or increased conflict. In Indigenous regions (i.e. Sápmi), mining threatens traditional economic practices, such as reindeer herding.

We illustrate the complexity and the challenges with governing and planning as it unfolds with regards to the Quartz mining in the Nasa Mountain in Nordland County, Northern Norway, and the impact it has on the quality of the decision-making process of local and national authorities. In this, we also showcase the numerous paradoxes that mineral-extraction in

Northern Norway raise, highlighting the importance of multilevel governance and multilevel planning (Stjernström et al 2018).

The Nasa Mountain Quartz-case

The proposed quartz mining project at Nasa Mountain in Rana municipality was first initiated in 2003. Over the twenty-year period following, the project saw a lengthy and contested planning process involving land-use regulation, environmental approvals, and Indigenous rights.

Although the local municipality approved the regulation plan submitted by Elkem ASA, it faced strong objections from regional authorities, Nordland County and the Sámi Parliament due to environmental concerns and conflicts with reindeer husbandry. The site overlaps with grazing areas used by both Norwegian and Swedish Sámi districts, also raising cross-border legal and cultural issues.

Despite revisions to the plan, concerns persisted about the impact on reindeer migration, noise pollution, and a violation of the Sami rights (Planning and Building Act 2008).

Figure 1 Map over Nasa Mountain Quartz Mine at the border between Nordland County in Norway and Arjeplog County in Sweden. Source: Kommunekart

ACTORS IN THE NASA MOUNTAIN QUARTZ CASE

Elkem ASA: The mining company leading the project. Responsible for submitting regulation plans and conducting impact assessments. It seeks to develop the site to supply quartz for silicon production.

Rana Municipality: The local authority that approved the regulation plan, initiating the formal land-use process under Norway's Planning and Building Act.

County Governor of Nordland: A key regional actor who raised objections based on environmental concerns and reindeer husbandry impacts. The Governor also oversees regional Sámi interests.

Norwegian Sámi Parliament: Represents Indigenous concerns, emphasizing the cultural and economic importance of reindeer herding and opposing the plan's impact on grazing lands.

Swedish Sámi Districts: Three districts affected by cross-border grazing rights, protected under a bilateral convention between Norway and Sweden.

Ministry of Local Government and Modernization (KMD): Ultimately approved the regulation plan in 2016, balancing national interests in mineral extraction against Sámi rights, with conditions to mitigate seasonal impacts.

Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries (NFD) and Ministry of Agriculture and Food (LMD): Acknowledged negative consequences for Sámi communities but supported the project based on its strategic value, proposing conditions to safeguard grazing access.

Sweco (Consultancy Firm): Conducted impact assessments in 2018, concluding that mining would cause moderate to high disruption to reindeer herding due to noise, dust, and barriers.

In 2016, the Norwegian Ministry of Local Government and Modernization approved the regulation plan with some conditions, prioritizing mineral interests over Sámi concerns. This decision triggered further processes, including land expropriation and impact assessments. In 2018, Elkem ASA commissioned Sweco to assess the effects on reindeer husbandry. The report concluded that mining would cause moderate to high disruption due to noise, dust, and barriers, particularly affecting herd movement and calf marking for Swedish Sámi districts.

The impact case was then lifted to national authorities, but also at this level the issue of the planning process was split between departments. While the question of environmental impacts was handled by the Environmental Directorate, another department handled the question of Indigenous rights. As a result, the policy- decision lacked coordination and a more comprehensive view of what was at stake.

In sum, the case reflects broader tensions between local indigenous rights and global sustainability goals and EU's Green Deal. This is similar to the Fosen wind farm ruling in 2021, where Norway's Supreme Court found that energy development violated Sámi cultural rights (Stjernström et al 2024).

The planning process with regards to the Nasa Mountain Quartz case raised several contradictions or paradoxes.

1. Many critical minerals are mined in countries with poor labour conditions and environmental harm. Europe relies heavily on these imports, prompting calls for domestic extraction in places like Norway, where standards are higher. This creates a moral argument for 'sustainable minerals' but also raises questions about how local communities should respond to global injustices tied to resource supply chains.

Figure 2 Areas of reindeer herding at Saltfjellet, near Nasa Mountain. Pixabay Free Photo.

2. Europe aims to reduce its reliance on China for critical minerals. However, the Nasa Mountain mining project is led by Elkem ASA, a Norwegian company with a majority owned by Chinese owned Bluestar, highlighting the contradiction of promoting resource independence while enabling Chinese control over Norwegian mineral assets. This

paradox raises concerns about national security, ownership of critical infrastructure, and the need for more strategic oversight in resource governance.

3. The global push for green technologies increases demand for rare minerals, often leading to local land-use conflicts. While mining is promoted as essential for sustainability, projects face opposition due to environmental concerns and impacts on Indigenous land use. What's considered sustainable at national or global levels may not be viewed as sustainable locally. This shows a disconnect between broad policy goals and community realities.
4. The border paradox in Indigenous rights is illustrated by the Sámi people's cross-border reindeer husbandry between Norway and Sweden. With the Nasa site sitting on the border between Norway and Sweden. Although protected by the 1751 Lappish Codicil, legal uncertainty and failed renegotiations, especially after the 1972 Reindeer Husbandry Convention, have led to frustration among Sámi communities and government bodies.
5. Finally, the planning process itself appeared to be fragmented, and full of both overlapping legal systems and various international obligations (including Norway's commitment to ILO Convention 169) that became partly contradictory to each-other, as well as to more national priorities and local concerns.

The Need for Multilevel Planning and Governance

Regional and spatial planning are strategic processes aimed at organizing land use, infrastructure, and development across broader geographic areas, often beyond individual municipal boundaries. These planning approaches seek to balance economic growth, environmental sustainability, and social equity by coordinating policies and investments across multiple jurisdictions. It also encompasses both formal statutory plans and informal governance arrangements, involving a wide range of stakeholders in participatory and deliberative processes (Levin-Keitel & Behrend, 2023; Stead, 2021).

Today, planning operates within a complex system of national and international policies. This layered system often leads to overlapping, and sometimes conflicting, decision-making processes. In the case of Nasa Mountain Quartz mining this includes conflicting local and national interests, international law, regional and European ambitions, as well as conflicting interests between various actors both between levels of governance, but also within various levels (Stjernström et al 2024). This complexity requires coordination across multiple levels of governance (Lidskog & Elander, 2010), often referred to as multilevel governance (Hooghe and Marks, 2001) and multilevel planning (Stjernström et al 2018).

The complexity underpinning the question of whether Norwegian national and local authorities should approve Quartz-mining at Nasa Mountain demands a multilevel and more coherent and

comprehensive regional and spatial planning process than what has taken place to date. This also has implications far beyond the case of Nasa Mountain.

Conclusion

Altogether, the Nasa Mountain case is a good illustration of the planning challenges and resulting paradoxes involved in the implementation of the green transformation. It also illustrates the shortcomings in our understanding of the complexity of planning and decision-making at different geographical levels. Moving forward, policy-makers should implement a formalized multilevel governance framework that integrates local, regional, and national decision-making processes, and across departments, and ensure that its adoption is mandatory in all planning of mineral-extraction projects.

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